

**To the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of
Azerbaijan, Comrade G. A. Aliyev**

(English Translation)

The construction of the first stage of the Trans-Iranian gas pipeline, with a capacity of more than 10.0 billion cubic meters per year, will lead to a significant increase in gas consumption and an acceleration of gasification rates for both industrial enterprises and public utilities.

Furthermore, in August of this year, the design of the underground gas storage facility located at the Garadagneft enterprise (Galmaz field) with a useful capacity of 1.2 billion cubic meters will be completed, and construction will immediately begin.

At present, on the territory of Azerbaijan, under the jurisdiction of the Transcaucasian Directorate of Main Gas Pipelines of the Ministry of Gas Industry of the USSR, the construction of main gas pipelines is being completed. Their total length will amount to 1,415 km with diameters ranging from 720 to 1,220 mm, including six booster compressor stations — one in Kazi-Magomed (Hajikabul), one in Agdam, two in Kazakh, and two in Galmaz — as well as fourteen gas distribution stations.

Thus, the volume of the gas facilities managed by the Transcaucasian Directorate of Main Gas Pipelines, only within our republic, will be twice its current volume (excluding the Azerbaijan SSR).

It should also be noted that technical supervision over the construction of the Trans-Iranian gas pipeline, the underground storage facility, compressor stations, gas distribution stations, and other structures is not carried out by the republic, while the Transcaucasian Directorate located in Tbilisi, due to its remoteness, is unable to ensure full and proper supervision.

All this complex infrastructure requires on-site operational management and coordination of all production and technical issues related both to the reception and

distribution of Iranian gas and to the operation of the gas storage facility, as well as the resolution of all matters connected with the Ministry of Oil Production of the Azerbaijan SSR, the Main Gas Administration under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, the Baku branch of "VNIGaz," the Azerbaijan State Gasoline Plant, and the Ministry of Gas Industry of the USSR.

We believe that there is now an urgent need to establish the Azerbaijan Directorate of Main Gas Pipelines of the USSR Ministry of Gas Industry, with its headquarters located in the city of Baku.

We kindly ask you to consider this matter and, if you approve, to submit a petition to the Ministry of Gas Industry of the USSR for the establishment of the aforementioned Directorate.

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